

Research

Long-term Trends and Demographic Risk Factors Attributed to Maternal Disorders Incidence in Five African Countries

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Abstract: Understanding the epidemiological characteristics of maternal disorders incidence (MDI) is highly important in designing policies to improve maternal health. This study investigates the long-term trends, and demographic risk factors associated with MDI. Data between 1990-2019 was obtained from the Global Burden of Diseases for the Republic of Cameroon (CAM), the Central African Republic (CAR), the Republic of Congo (COG), the Democratic Republic of the Congo (DRC), and the Republic of Chad (TCD). Joinpoint regression was employed to determine the different behaviors of the trends. The Age-Period-Cohort statistical model was applied in the determination of demographic risks associated with age, period, and cohort; and Holt's double exponential model was utilized in the forecast of the trends. MDI declined mostly in COG by 1.7% (95% CI: 1.7; 1.8) between 1990 and 2019 based on the Joinpoint regression. In TCD, MDI rates remained steady in 2019 compared to 1990. In the five countries, MDI rates were most prevalent in women aged between 20-29. The age, period, and cohort rate ratios declined the most in CAM by nearly 5, 3, and 22 folds respectively. The age category between 15-34 years, the period before 2005, and the cohorts born before 1975 were at higher risks. Based on the forecasted trends, MDI rates were identified to be highly significant in the five countries, and TCD registered the highest rates in 2030. Declining maternal disorders incidence in low- and middle-income countries requires the adoption and employment of new health strategies and policies.

Keywords: Maternal disorders incidence; Reproductive health; Maternal health; Demographic risk factors, African countries.

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1. Introduction

The health of mothers and fetuses can be negatively impacted by many medical conditions during pregnancy [1]. Pregnancy complications or maternal disorders are sometimes developed by healthy women before pregnancy, and they include anaemia, infections, depression, anxiety, high blood pressure, pregnancy diabetes, hyperemesis gravidarum, etc. [1,2]. Between 1990 and 2015, maternal disorders have contributed to a significant number of deaths among the female gender aged from 15 to 49 years (reproductive age) worldwide, with the largest contribution coming from low and middle-income countries [3].

The Republic of Cameroon (CAM), the Central African Republic (CAR), the Republic of Congo (COG), the Democratic Republic of Congo (DRC), and the Republic of Chad (TCD) are countries belonging to the central African region [4]. According to the World Bank country classifications by national income level in 2022, CAM and COG are classified as lower-middle-income countries, although CAR, DRC, and TCD are identified as low-income countries [5]. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), fifteen (15) countries, including those from central Africa region were considered to be at “*high alert*” and “*very high alert*” levels because of the incidence and mortality caused by maternal disorders in women during 2017 [6].

One of the sustainable development goals (SDGs) is to decline the maternal mortality ratio (MMR) to 70 per 100,000 births globally, with no country presenting more than twice that value in 2030 [3]. Therefore, understanding and providing quality management for maternal disorders is of major importance in declining MMR and ensuring quality reproductive health. Many studies were conducted regarding maternal mortality and morbidity in different African countries and demonstrated the high burden of maternal disorders in sub-Saharan countries [7-10]. However, there were fewer records of studies exploring the incidence of maternal disorders incidence (MDI) in central African countries, especially at a national level. Hence, we undertake this study to contribute to the strategies and policy implementations relative to maternal and reproductive health. Our study aims to explore the epidemiological characteristics of maternal disorders incidence MDI between 1990 and 2019 in five central African countries. To achieve this goal, we investigated the long-term trends and the demographic risk factors relative to age, period, and birth cohort in the five African countries (CAM, CAR, COG, DRC, and TCD).

2. Methods

2.1 Data Source

MDI rates, MDI counts, and the population numbers used in the study were extracted from the Global Burden of Diseases (GBD) 2019 [11]. The incidence counts and rates represented all causes of maternal disorders in CAM, CAR, COG, DRC, and TCD. Rates were evaluated per 100,000 people. The GBD database is controlled by the Institute for Health Metrics and Evaluation (IHME) based in Seattle, Washington State, USA. Primary sources of data for GBD include household surveys with complete birth histories, censuses, vital registrations, disease surveillance systems, and sample registration systems. The data used for the research is located in GBD data input under the Global Health Data Exchange (GHDx) section in the results tools. Ethical approval was not needed for this study because there was no direct involvement of human subjects.

2.2 Statistical analyses

2.2.1 Joinpoint Regression model

The variations in the trends of MDI in CAM, CAR, Chad, and DRC during 1990-2019 were investigated using Joinpoint regression. Years with significant changes in the patterns were identified, and the annual percentage change (APC) and the average annual percent change (AAPC) along with their 95% confidence interval (CI) were also estimated for each trend segment between 1990-2019 [12]. The Joinpoint regression model equation is presented as follows:

$$E[y_i|x_i] = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \cdot x_1 + \gamma_1(x_i - \tau_1)^+ + \dots + \gamma_n(x_i - \tau_k)^+ \quad (1)$$

$\beta_0, \beta_1, y_1, \dots, y_n$ represent the regression coefficients; $ik, \kappa < n$ represents the unknown Joinpoint [12]. The algorithm for the Joinpoint regression analysis calculations is described elsewhere [12]. The study utilized the Joinpoint regression program version 4.9.0.0 (March 2021) from the Statistical Research and Application branch of the Surveillance Research Program of the U.S. National Cancer Institute to conduct the Joinpoint regression analysis.

2.2. 2 Age-Period-Cohort statistical model

MDI rates were evaluated using the Age-Period-Cohort (APC) statistical model analysis. The age effects represent different risks during various periods of life. Period effects indicate population-wide exposure at a specific point in time, and different risks in various birth cohorts are reflected mainly by cohort effects [13,14]. To isolate the distinct contributions of age, period, and cohort, we decomposed the age and cycled a queue into their linear and nonlinear constituents [15]. This decomposition also generates many essential functions such as net drift, local drifts, longitudinal age trends, period deviation, and cohort deviation [16]. The local drifts represent the annual percentage changes in each age group, and the net drift shows the overall annual percentage changes in the adjusted age group (age category) over time. The longitudinal age curve is adjusted for period deviations and represents the fitted longitudinal age-specific rates in the reference cohort. Period relative risk (RR) is defined as the period risk ratio adjusted for age and nonlinear cohort contributions of each period compared to the reference period. The cohort relative risk (RR) defines the cohort risk ratio adjusted for age and nonlinear period contributions in each cohort with the reference period [17].

MDI rates and demographic statistics were decomposed into five consecutive years before conducting the APC analysis. They were arranged from 1990-1994 (median 1992.5) to 2015-2019 (median 2017.5). Consecutive five-year age groups were set from 15-19 (median 17.5) to 45-49 (median 47.5). The birth cohort arrangements concerned those born from 1945-2004 and were also divided into 5 consecutive years for the APC analysis. The reference values were selected as the lower two central values in the event of an equal number of categories. Wald chi-square tests were conducted with a p-value set at $P < 0.01$ for statistical significance.

While the APC model analysis has advantages, it also suffers from limitations such as the uncertainty principle and identification problems [17]. The uncertainty principle indicates the measurements of absolute rates in cohorts that are not frequently taken into account by epidemiological cohort and case-control researchers [17]. The identifiability problem is the fact that the three scales are collinear from the equation cohort equals period minus age. Thus, the log-linear trends in the rates cannot only be represented by the contributions of age, period, and cohort [14]. The equation representing the APC model is displayed as follows:

$$\mathit{Cohort} = \mathit{Period} - \mathit{Age} \quad (2)$$

The APC Web Tool (Biostatistics Branch, National Cancer Institute, Bethesda, MD, USA) software was utilized to oversee the APC statistical analysis.

2.2.3 Holt's Double Exponential Smoothing model

Holt's two-parameter model is a popular smoothing model for projecting data with trends. The model has three separate equations that work together to generate a final forecast [18,19]. Holt's double exponential smoothing model is established on a moving average of the previous values, allowing the smoothed current value to be applied to forecast the next value [18,19]. It is used for forecasting where there is no seasonality and utilizes two parameters [18,19]. The first parameter is for the overall smoothing, and the second parameter is for the trend smoothing equation [18]. The equation for the forecasting model is presented as follows [19]:

$$\hat{Y} = L_{t-1} + T_{t-1} \quad (3)$$

With L_t being the estimated level generated by

$$L_t = \alpha Y_t + (1 - \alpha)(L_{t-1} + T_t - 1) \quad (4)$$

Where T_t is the estimated slope as:

$$T_t = \beta(L_t - L_{t-1}) + (1 - \beta)T_{t-1} \quad (5)$$

α and β

represent the smoothing parameters. According to the dataset that was recorded from 1990 to 2019, 80% was used as the training set (1990 to 2013), and 20% was used as the testing set (2014 to 2019). Holt's double exponential smoothing was first conducted through manual tuning of the two smoothing parameters (alpha and beta), followed by an optimum parameter tuning model to decrease the root mean square errors (RMSE) [20]. In all models, the optimum value tuning parameter was 0.5, and accuracy was assessed through the mean absolute percentage error estimates (MAPE) [20]. Further details on algorithms and calculations are discussed elsewhere [19,20]. RStudio 2022.07.1 for Windows was used to forecast the incidence of maternal disorders trends.

3. Results

3.1 Joinpoint regression analysis: Trends behavior

Figure 1 presents the crude incidence rates (CIR) and the age-standardized incidence rates (ASIR) of maternal disorders from 1990 to 2019. Based on the different trends, the patterns of CIR and ASIR in each country presented similarities. Declining patterns with upward and downward patterns could be observed. During 1990, COG and DRC had the least and the highest incidence rates in contrast to the rest of the countries. In 2019, TCD recorded the highest incidence rates of maternal disorders. Meanwhile, COG still presented the lowest rate among the rest of the countries. An explosive upward behaviour was observed in TCD between 2000 and 2010 before decreasing.

Table 1 displays the annual percentage of change (APC) and the average annual percent change (AAPC) values of MDI generated from the Joinpoint regression analysis. According to the table, upward and downward APC values could be identified in the five countries. Except for TCD which presented positive APC values, the rest of the countries showed only negative APC values. The values of the AAPC demonstrated that MDI declined the most in COG followed by CAM between 1990 to 2019. In TCD, the value of the AAPC was nearly 0.0 percent (0.0%), suggesting a non-decline behaviour.

3.2 Age, Period, and Cohort statistical analysis: Demographic risk factors

3.2.1 Local Drifts and Net Drifts

The local drifts represent the annual percentage changes in each age group, and the net drift is defined as the overall annual percentage change of the adjusted age group (age category) over time (1990-2019).

Figure 2 displays the local drift of MDI from the five countries in women aged between 15-19 and 45-49 years. According to the trends in each country, upward and downward behaviours are observed in different patterns representing CAM, CAR, COG, and DRC. In TCD, a gradually increasing behaviour could be observed in the pattern. The annual percentage change values in each age group (local drifts) were the lowest in CAM, in comparison with the rest of the countries.

Table 2 is the representation of MDI net drift values in women aged between 15-49 years from 1990 to 2019. According to the net drift values, CAM displayed the highest decreasing value, followed by COG. TCD registered the lowest percentage among the countries between 1990 and 2019.

3.2.2 Rates per age group and Age relative risk (Age RR)

Figure 3 shows the rates of MDI in each age group from 15-19 to 45-49 years. TCD listed the highest curves in comparison to all the rest of the countries. CAM, CAR, COG, and DRC registered the highest and lowest rates in all age groups during 1990-1994 and 2015-2019, respectively. In TCD, the highest rates were observed during 2005-2009; and the lowest rates were between 1995 to 1999. In CAR and COG, the age group of 20-24 registered the highest MDI rates in

comparison to other age groups during the study period. CAM and TCD displayed their highest rates in the age group of 25-29 years between 1990 to 2019. In DRC, the age group of 25-29 held the highest MDI rates between 1990-2014. Meanwhile, the age group of 30-34 years listed the highest rates of MDI during 2015-2019.

The age rate ratios (age RR) of MDI and their 95% confidence intervals are presented in figure 4. There were rapid declining patterns in all five countries, and the highest rate ratio was observed in the 15-19 age group. CAM listed the highest rate ratio followed by COG in the same age group (15-19 years) when compared to the rest of the countries. The age RR declined the most in CAM by nearly 5 folds. The least decline was identified in TCD with approximately 2.4 folds. When considering the age groups from 15-19 to 45-49 years, the age groups under 35 years were determined as the groups at higher risk of MDI in all the five countries based on the age RR values.

3.2.3 Period relative risk (Period RR)

The rapid decreasing patterns in the trends of the period rate ratios (period RR) in all five countries were as presented in figure 5. CAM and COG displayed the highest rate ratios during 1990-1994 among the five countries. CAM showed the greatest decline of period RR with almost 3.9-folds. The decrease in CAR and TCD was similar around 2.2 folds. Based on the decomposition of the period (1990-1994 to 2015-2019), the period before 2005 was evaluated as the period with a higher risk of MDI in the five countries.

3.2.4 Cohort relative risk (Cohort RR)

Figure 6 illustrates the cohort rate ratios (cohort RR) of MDI in the cohorts born from 1945-1949 to 2000-2004. All trends presented declining patterns. CAM listed the highest rate ratio in the cohort born between 1945-1949 in contrast with the rest of the countries. Accordingly, the cohort RR declined mostly by almost 22 folds in CAM, and the least decline occurred in TCD with nearly 5.5 folds. In all five countries, the cohorts born before 1975 were identified as the birth cohorts at higher risk of MDI.

3.3 Holt's Double Exponential Smoothing model analysis: Trends Forecast

Table 3 displays Holt's model estimates from the manual and the optimal tuning parameters. According to RMSE values, Holt's model from manual tuning displayed lower estimates in contrast to the optimum model statistics. In TCD, the RMSE estimates from testing samples presented lower values in comparison to the training sample. MAPE estimates in manual tuning parameters showed lower values in both the training and the testing dataset in comparison with the optimum models, except for TCD. Although RMSE and MAPE values increased in Holt's optimum models, the accuracy percentages represented by MAPE estimates were all lower than 3%. In addition, the values of the testing dataset were between the 95% confidence intervals of the forecasted values.

Figure 7 showed the forecasted trends of MDI in the five countries. Based on the respective trends, CAM, CAR, COG, and DRC presented declining patterns between 2019 to 2030. However, the trend in TCD displayed a slow decline between 2019 and 2030. Based on the forecasted values, MDI rates between 1990 and 2030 will decline by nearly 2.5 folds, 1.6 times, and 1-fold in CAM, CAR, and TCD, respectively. COG and DRC presented the same declining fold by nearly 2.2 in 2030 compared to 1990.

Figure 1. Crude incidence rates (CIR) and age-standardized incidence rates (ASIR) of maternal disorders

Figure 2. Local drift trends of maternal disorders incidence and their 95% confidence intervals

Figure 3. Maternal disorders incidence rates per age groups

Figure 4. Age rate ratios (RR) of maternal disorders incidence and their 95% confidence intervals

Figure 5. Period rate ratios (RR) of maternal disorders incidence and their 95% confidence intervals

Figure 6. Cohort rate ratios (RR) of maternal disorders incidence and their 95% confidence intervals

Figure 7. Forecasted trends of maternal disorders incidence

Table 1. APC and AAPC values and their 95% confidence intervals (CI)

Segments	CAM		CAR		COG		DRC		TCD	
	Year	APC (95% CI)								
MDI										
Trend 1	1990-1994	-1.7*(-1.8; -1.5)	1990-1993	-0.8*(-0.9; -0.7)	1994-1994	-2.4*(-2.6; -2.2)	1990-2005	-0.6*(-0.6; -0.6)	1990-1995	-0.2*(-0.3; -0.2)
Trend 2	1994-1998	-0.6*(-0.8; -0.3)	1993-2004	-0.7*(-0.7; -0.7)	1994-1999	-1.5*(-1.7; -1.3)	2005-2008	-1.2*(-1.6; -0.9)	1995-1998	-0.3*(-0.6; -0.1)
Trend 3	1998-2006	-0.1*(-0.2; -0.1)	2004-2010	-1.0*(-1.0; -0.9)	1999-2008	-0.5*(-0.6; -0.5)	2008-2011	-1.9*(-2.3; -1.5)	1998-2001	0.2(-0.1; 0.4)
Trend 4	2006-2012	-2.2*(-2.3; -2.1)	2010-2014	-1.4*(-1.5; -1.3)	2008-2013	-1.7*(-1.9; -1.5)	2011-2014	-2.6*(-3.0; -2.2)	2001-2004	3.2*(3.0; 3.5)
Trend 5	2012-2017	-3.5*(-3.6; -3.3)	2014-2017	-1.9*(-2.0; -1.7)	2013-2017	-3.7*(-4.0; -3.4)	2014-2017	-3.9*(-4.3; -3.6)	2004-2007	0.0(-0.2; 0.3)
Trend 6	2017-2019	-2.6*(-3.0; -2.2)	2017-2019	-1.3*(-1.5; -1.1)	2017-2019	-2.6*(-3.3; -2.0)	2017-2019	-2.8*(-3.2; -2.4)	2007-2019	-0.6*(-0.7; -0.6)
AAPC	1990-2019	-1.6*(-1.6; -1.5)	1990-2019	-1.0*(-1.0; -1.0)	1990-2019	-1.7*(-1.8; -1.7)	1990-2019	-1.5*(-1.6; -1.4)	1990-2019	0.0(0.0; 0.0)

MDI maternal disorders incidence, APC annual percentage change, AAPC average annual percent change, CI confidence interval. *Values statistically significant at alpha = 0.05.

Table 2. Net drift values and their 95% confidence intervals (CI)

Country	Net drift	95% CI
CAM	-5.27	(-5.45; -5.09)

CAR	-3.1905	(-3.31; -3.06)
COG	-4.86	(-5.02; -4.70)
DRC	-4.12	(-4.27; -3.98)
TCD	-3.00	(-3.03; -2.96)

CI confidence interval

Table 3. Holt’s Double Exponential Smoothing model estimates

Country	Holt’s model	Dataset	RMSE	MAPE
CAM	Original model	Training	57.46	0.29
		Test	80.83	0.73
	Optimum model	Training	60.77	0.39
		Test	135.84	1.22
CAR	Original model	Training	7.70	0.05
		Test	58.79	0.43
	Optimum model	Training	11.53	0.07
		Test	100.97	0.81
COG	Original model	Training	26.74	0.21
		Test	178.42	1.88
	Optimum model	Training	44.09	0.35
		Test	323.49	3.53
DRC	Original model	Training	20.29	0.11
		Test	234.19	1.80
	Optimum model	Training	34.35	0.17
		Test	351.41	2.77

	Original model	Training	101.37	0.34
TCD		Test	12.18	0.05
	Optimum model	Training	141.59	0.50
		Test	25.85	0.14

RMSE; root mean square error, MAPE; mean absolute percentage of error

4. Discussion

This study conducted on maternal disorders incidence (MDI) between 1990 to 2019, investigated the trends through a Joinpoint regression analysis, the demographic risks factors associated with age, period, and birth cohort using the Age-Period-Cohort (APC) statistical model in five African countries (CAM, CAR, COG, DRC, and TCD). Moreover, the study forecasted the trends for the year 2030 based on Holt’s double exponential smoothing model.

The Joinpoint regression model generated the annual percentage change (APC) and the average annual percent change (AAPC) estimates. The values of the APC indicate both upward and downward patterns in the trends of MDI during different years. However, only upward values were reported for TCD, compared with the other countries. The AAPC values demonstrated declining trends of MDI in most of the countries, except for TCD where the percentage was around 0.0%. In COG, the percentage illustrated the highest decreasing trend among the countries between 1990 to 2019. The decline of MDI rates in the respective countries might be justified by efforts made by respective governments and international partners to improve maternal and reproductive health by conducting educative campaigns about sexual behaviour, healthy lifestyle, promoting antenatal care, recruiting and forming healthcare givers such as physicians and midwives, providing healthcare infrastructures, protecting women against gender-based and sexual violence, and integrating and encouraging family planning as demonstrated in previous studies and reports [21-25]. It is important to mention that the outcomes of the implemented policies, strategies, and programs differ in every country, which may result in the unequal repartition of the declining percentage values.

The Age-Period-Cohort (APC) statistical model analysis produced both local drifts and net drifts. The local drifts represent the annual percentage changes in each age group (15-19 to 45-49 years), and the net drift is defined as the overall annual percentage changes of the adjusted age group (15-49 years) over time (1990 to 2019). The local drift values showed increasing and decreasing percentages of change in different age groups across the five countries. Meanwhile, the overall annual percentage of change demonstrated that MDI decreased mostly in COG among the age category of 15-49 years. Conversely, TCD had the least declining trend in the age category of 15-49 years between 1990 to 2019 in comparison to the rest of the countries. The highest decline in MDI rates identified in COG might be associated with the fact that the government in COG is devoted to free maternal and child healthcare services, and an increase in contraceptive usage that has been revealed by the United Nations Population Fund (UNFPA) report [23]. In TCD, the least decline of MDI rates might be associated with socioeconomic and demographic factors such as poverty, limited health infrastructure, and early marriage that had been mentioned by a report of the UNFPA in 2021 [25]. Among women aged between 20-29 years, MDI rates were the highest according to the study. This finding might be explained by the unhealthy lifestyle, low rate of literacy, poverty, and sexually transmitted diseases such as HIV/AIDS that are highly associated with this age group; and which interact negatively with women’s health as revealed in other studies [26,27]. Furthermore, the study revealed that women aged under 35 years were at higher risk of MDI relative to the age rate ratios. The identification of women aged under 35 years as the category of women being at higher risk of MDI in the five central African countries might be related to the reason that the peak of reproductive age in women was

demonstrated to be before and in their late twenties (20's), and that fertility decreases from their thirties thus, making natural pregnancy unlikely [28]. Therefore, as fertility decreases with the increase of age, relative risks associated with pregnancy also decline [28]. According to the period and the birth cohort relative risks, the period before 2005, and the cohorts born before 1975 were identified to be at higher risks of MDI respectively. The decline of the period's relative risks might be attributed to different efforts made by the respective governments in promoting quality maternal health in women over many years, with the collaboration of international and national organizations [21-25]. These efforts include the development of strategies and policies towards improvement of reproductive health indicators in urban and rural areas, regardless of the unequal repartition of the outcomes. Because period effects can have an impact on certain age categories causing an indirect cohort effect, and people from various cohorts born in separate periods can cause uncertainty about the period association in some ways, it is nearly difficult to decompose the interpretation of those two models [17]. Consequently, the decline of the cohort's relative risks is associated with the efforts implemented over many years in providing maternal and reproductive health across the countries during different periods.

Based on the results of Holt's double exponential model used in the forecast, MDI will decrease by 2030, although the rates will still be high in all five countries. The trends in CAM and TCD will respectively experience the largest and least downward patterns during 2030 among the five central African countries compared to 1990. Many studies revealed that antenatal care performance is low in many African countries and this low implementation is associated with socio-economic and demographic factors such as unwillingness to visit healthcare facilities, getting permission for antenatal care, low availability of healthcare facilities and their cost, and lack of education in the population [29,30]. Considering these findings, this study recommends that respective governments and health organization partners should invest more efforts in designing more efficient strategies and policies to improve maternal and reproductive healthcare coverage, increase the availability of health infrastructures, especially in rural areas; as well as increasing campaigns to promote a healthy lifestyle, trust in healthcare providers, antenatal care attendance, and responsible sexual behaviour among young adult and adult females. Governments should establish and apply laws to protect women against domestic and sexual violence, early marriage, and gender mutilation, relative to socioeconomic and demographic factors. Female gender empowerment, free maternal care, and educational campaigns for the use of contraceptives to control fertility rates should be a part of the core design of different strategies to decrease maternal disorders burden and ensure quality maternal and reproductive health.

There were some limitations in the study. Firstly, this article does not analyse separately different forms of MDI. Secondly, the limitation is related to the identifiability and uncertainty principle of the Age-Period-Cohort (APC) model analysis. These parameters could not be avoided because the description of results from an individual's level is not necessarily large for the explanation at the population level. However, some studies [26,27] were conducted using the APC model as the authors did in this study. Finally, the third limitation is associated with Holt's double exponential smoothing model. Although the estimates of the root mean square errors (RMSE) and mean absolute percentage errors (MAPE) in the optimum parameters of Holt's models were higher compared to the manual parameters, the values of the training dataset were within the confidence interval of the forecasted values. Consequently, different models should be employed to forecast MDI trends in future studies.

5. Conclusion

Our findings reveal that MDI declined mostly in women of reproductive age of the five central African countries between 1990 and 2019. The age factor demonstrated that women under the age of 35 years had the highest incidence rates and were identified as the age category at higher risk of MDI. Based on the forecast finding, MDI will decline during 2030 compared to 2019 in CAM, CAR, COG, and DRC although the rates were considerably high. In TCD, MDI trend during 2030 showed a steady pattern in comparison and with the highest rates when compared to the rest of the countries. New strategies and policies relative to maternal and reproductive health should be employed in different countries. Respective governments should reinforce and produce more efforts by elaborating and adopting laws to

protect women against socioeconomic and demographic factors. A large-scale study and investigation of MDI subgroups should be carried out in the future to corroborate the hypothesis relative to this study.

List of abbreviation

AAPC:	Average Annual Percent Change
APC:	Annual Percentage Change
APC model:	Age-Period-Cohort model
ASIR:	Age-standardized Incidence Rate
CAM:	Republic of Cameroon
CAR:	Central African Republic
CI:	Confidence Interval
CIR:	Crude Incidence Rate
COG:	Republic of Congo
DRC:	Democratic Republic of the Congo
GBD:	Global Burden of Diseases
GHDx:	Global Health Data Exchange
HIV/AIDS:	Human Immunodeficiency Virus/Acquired Immunodeficiency Syndrome
MAPE:	Mean Absolute Percentage Errors
MDI:	Maternal Disorders Incidence
MMR:	Maternal Mortality Ratio
RMSE:	Root Mean Square Errors
RR:	Risk Ratio, Relative Risks,
SDGs:	Sustainable Development Goals
UNFPA:	United Nations Population Fund
U.S. A:	United States of America
WHO:	World Health Organization

Declarations

Author Contributions: Conceptualization, NTM, ASJ, NNN, IAK, CHY; methodology, NTM; software, NTM; validation, NTM, ASJ, NNN, IAK, CHY; formal analysis, NTM; investigation, NTM, ASJ, NNN; resources, NTM, NNN; data curation, NTM; writing—original draft preparation, NTM, ASJ, NNN; writing—review and editing, NTM, ASJ, NNN, IAK, CHY; visualization, NTM, CHY; supervision; project administration, NTM, ASJ, NNN, IAK, CHY. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

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